

Diff(S_6): Integer sequence generation

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A previous article [1] detailed the 720 elements of the symmetric group S_6 – all the permutations of 123456. Treated as decimal numbers and sorted in increasing order, this group is composed of six subgroups, each beginning with a lead integer 1, 2, ..., 6. Curiously, the first difference within each subgroup – when divided by 9 – yields integer sequences.

Below is the full list of the results; in each table the integers are arranged in 12 rows wrapped around left-to-right. The difference sequence with lead number 1 and 6 are identical so only the first is included.

dsq1	1	9	2	9	1	78	1	19	3
8	2	77	2	8	3	19	1	78	1
9	2	9	1	657	1	9	2	9	1
178	1	29	4	7	3	66	2	18	4
18	2	67	1	19	3	8	2	646	1
19	3	8	2	67	1	29	4	7	3
176	3	7	4	29	1	67	2	8	3
19	1	646	2	8	3	19	1	67	2
18	4	18	2	66	3	7	4	29	1
178	1	9	2	9	1	657	1	9	2
9	1	78	1	19	3	8	2	77	2
8	3	19	1	78	1	9	2	9	1

dsq2	1	9	2	9	1	78	1	19	3
8	2	77	2	8	3	19	1	78	1
9	2	9	1	1657	1	9	2	9	1
278	1	39	5	6	4	55	2	28	5
17	3	56	1	29	4	7	3	535	1
19	3	8	2	167	1	39	5	6	4
165	3	17	5	28	2	56	2	18	4
18	2	535	2	8	3	19	1	167	2
28	5	17	3	55	3	17	5	28	2
167	1	19	3	8	2	546	1	9	2
9	1	178	1	29	4	7	3	66	2
18	4	18	2	67	1	19	3	8	2

dsq3	1	9	2	9	1	178	1	29	4
7	3	66	2	18	4	18	2	67	1
19	3	8	2	546	1	9	2	9	1
278	1	39	5	6	4	55	2	28	5
17	3	56	1	29	4	7	3	1635	1
29	4	7	3	56	1	39	5	6	4
275	4	6	5	39	1	56	3	7	4
29	1	525	2	18	4	18	2	56	2
28	5	17	3	165	4	6	5	39	1
167	2	8	3	19	1	536	1	19	3
8	2	67	1	29	4	7	3	176	3
7	4	29	1	67	2	8	3	19	1

dsq4	1	19	3	8	2	67	1	29	4
7	3	176	3	7	4	29	1	67	2
8	3	19	1	536	1	19	3	8	2
167	1	39	5	6	4	165	3	17	5
28	2	56	2	18	4	18	2	525	1
29	4	7	3	56	1	39	5	6	4
275	4	6	5	39	1	56	3	7	4
29	1	1635	3	7	4	29	1	56	3
17	5	28	2	55	4	6	5	39	1
278	1	9	2	9	1	546	2	8	3
19	1	67	2	18	4	18	2	66	3
7	4	29	1	178	1	9	2	9	1

dsq5	2	8	3	19	1	67	2	18	4
18	2	66	3	7	4	29	1	178	1
9	2	9	1	546	2	8	3	19	1
167	2	28	5	17	3	55	3	17	5
28	2	167	1	19	3	8	2	535	2
18	4	18	2	56	2	28	5	17	3
165	4	6	5	39	1	167	2	8	3
19	1	535	3	7	4	29	1	56	3
17	5	28	2	55	4	6	5	39	1
278	1	9	2	9	1	1657	1	9	2
9	1	78	1	19	3	8	2	77	2
8	3	19	1	78	1	9	2	9	1

Some observations follow.

- 1) Sequences dsq1, dsq2, dsq3, and dsq4 are well-known and listed in the On-line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS) as **A217626**; dsq5 appears new and has been submitted to the OEIS for inclusion, assigned as sequence **A370428**.
- 2) When each table is read out in columns (not rows) all generated sequences are new.
- 3) Scanned down as columns, the lists show small integers no more than 5 in alternating columns 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and integers 6 or (much) greater in the odd columns.
- 4) The palindromic string 19291 occurs in all tables, sometimes opening the list, closing the list, or both, as for dsq1.
- 5) Primes crop up throughout all tables; the biggest integer (1657) is indeed prime.
- 6) The logarithm of the vector string [dsq1 dsq2 dsq3 dsq4 dsq5], when summed cumulatively and then curvefit with a 3rd order polynomial, shows a residual with a clear sinusoidal behavior, interspersed with fractal spikes; see the image below.

The OCTAVE commands for these operations were:

```
logs=[log(dsq1) log(dsq2) log(dsq3) log(dsq4) log(dsq5)]; % composite of logs
csum=cumsum(logs); % cumulative sum of composite
x=1:1:595; % linear index string
fit=polyfit(x,csum,3); % 3rd order fit coefficients
pol=polyval(fit,x); % 3rd order polynomial result
res=pol-csum; % residual difference
plot(res,'-*'),grid % plot residual; the image is above
```

References

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'S₆: The whole enchilada and more', 10.5281/zenodo.10676430, 2024.